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CAPACITY BUILDING OF RUSSIAN UNIVERSITIES STAFF FOR THE DESIGN & DELIVERY OF PROSPECTIVE IT-ORIENTED ACADEMIC PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the results of the implementation of a pilot project for a large-scale professional development of 1000+ academics from 100+ Russian Universities at the International Computer Science CPD Center in National Research Tomsk State University. The training was fully implemented online in three educational areas: "Research & development in IT", "Advanced teaching & learning technologies", and "Academic programs of a new generation". In addition, the workshops called "End-to-End Digital Transformation Days" and two International Conferences on IT were organized. The programs on each track included the performance of individual and group projects. A special course "Key faculty competencies in the context of the academic program life cycle: Foresight-Forecast-Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate" was offered. The idea of the course is borrowed from the evolution of well-known CDIO approach to engineering education. The course objective was to develop competencies of academic staff of various positions for productive teamwork in university system of division of labor.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the National Program for the development of the Digital Economy, launched in Russia in 2017, the number of students enrolled in higher education programs in the field of IT (mathematics, computer science, digital technologies) may triple by 2024. This requires a substantial increase in a number of faculty members whose competencies are not inferior to the best international standards in these subject areas and meet the requirements to mastering up-to-date teaching & learning technologies.

Meeting this challenge the International Computer Science Continues Professional Development (CPD) Center was established in National Research Tomsk State University (TSU), one of the leading universities in Russia (<http://en.tsu.ru/>). The purpose of the CPD Center is to concentrate the research and educational potential in the field of mathematics, computer science and digital technologies for the development and implementation of advanced training programs for academic staff of universities in Russia and neighboring CIS countries. The idea is to achieve the goal by collaboration and networking with other Russian and foreign universities, research institutes and IT companies, as well as inviting well-known and respected IT experts.

Initially, it was planned to implement faculty training with the use of blended learning mode rotating on-campus and online sessions. However, restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic prevented the organization of on-campus sessions. Initial plan had been revised, and faculty training in 2020 was implemented fully online. This added work to create more online teaching & learning materials. At the same time, it allowed to expand the geographical area of universities participating in the pilot project and attracting more academics to the online training. As a result, the initial plan to train up to 200 faculty members was exceeded by five times. More than 1000 faculty members from 100+ universities were enrolled. The location of the universities participated in the pilot project on the geographical map is shown in Fig 1.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Section 1

Within the framework of the pilot project faculty training was realized in three tracks: "Research & development in IT area" (R&D), "Advanced teaching & learning technologies" (T&L), and "Academic programs of a new generation (AP)". Trainees had the opportunity to build individual educational paths within the tracks.

The idea of R&D-track was to develop faculty competencies in research & development to create a meaningful basis for academic programs in cooperation with IT companies. The main topics of lectures and master classes were the following: innovations in IT, immersion in a problem, terms of reference for a project, concept and project life cycle, group work methodology, creative thinking and

generation of new ideas, Agile project management according to the Scrum method, choosing the best project solution, communication with the customer, MVP and feedback, project presentation, support institutions and sources of project funding at the university, etc. The objective of the T&L-track was to master the advanced methods and technologies of teaching & learning at a modern university. Faculty members have got acquainted with the best practices of using such pedagogical techniques as Backward Design, Flipped Classroom, Gamification, Blended Learning, Peer Assessment, etc., as well as applying of various digital tools and LMS for online education, MOOCs development, etc. The aim of the AP-track was the comprehensive preparation of university faculty members for the design, implementation and quality assurance of IT-academic programs of three levels (undergraduate, graduate, postgraduate) at all stages of the program life cycle.

The training programs on each track included the performance of individual or group projects by the faculty members as trainees. As part of R&D-track, the trainees created a new scientific & technological foundation for a new educational product (discipline, interdisciplinary module, etc.) in IT area. Within T&L-track, the trainees developed new educational products applying new teaching & learning technologies. As part of AP-track, the trainees designed new academic programs most competitive in today's IT higher education market. The focus of all tracks was directed at the priorities of the selected end-to-end digital technologies (AI, Machine Learning, AR/VR, IoT, Big Data, Cybersecurity, etc.). This was realized, among other things, through field-specific master classes, as well as methodological and consulting support available to each trainee.

2.2 Section 2

The complete cycle of training lasted for 5 months from July to November 2020 according to the schedule shown in Fig 2. In the intervals between online training sessions, the trainees' self-study was organized, including project work. The methodological material for teaching & learning within each track was developed and implemented in the logic of project work according to the classical scheme: Analysis – Specification – Design – Development – Implementation. In parallel there were organized three online workshops called “End-to-End Digital Transformation Days” with active participation of representatives of leading IT companies. Remote interaction of trainees with each other and with instructors was carried out on the basis of the following principles: integration of personal and institutional virtual learning environment, flexibility of educational trajectories, the ability to check the educational results of trainees through the analysis of their digital footprints.

To enrich personal virtual learning environment, trainees had access to educational activities through organizers, messengers, network communities (WhatsApp, Facebook), and communicative tools for group interaction (Mirro, Trello, Mindmap). In parallel with the use of open Internet services, digital tools of institutional systems for support of distance learning technologies, including LMS, were used. Work in the LMS included the performance of assignments, consolidated into a single schedule

with deadlines, assessment criteria, examples, comments and other materials. A number of assignments were assessed with peer review made by trainees based on criteria and matrices prepared by the instructors.

3 RESULTS

For participation in the pilot project 1,012 trainees from 116 universities have been registered. The contingent of trainees was rather diverse. Majority (70%) of trainees were mainly engaged in teaching, and 30% were mainly engaged in research and management in IT departments at universities. The trainees included 64% of experienced instructors and researchers with academic degrees and 36% of young faculty members. It should be noted that two thirds of the trainees (66%) were female and only one third (34%) were male. Following various priorities, 63% of trainees registered for T&L-track, 20% for AP-track, and 17% for R&D-track.

Totally, 827 trainees mastered the training programs (more than 80% of registered trainees). About 40% of the trainees completed the full training cycle. The main results, i.e., the updated and developed trainees competencies, were demonstrated by them while working on R&D and educational projects carried out in the interests of their universities. On the R&D-track, 66 trainees (about 40% of those registered for the track) successfully completed program cycle and carried out 18 group projects. The relatively small number of R&D-track graduates is due to the fact that only 6% of all registered trainees were researchers and, therefore, directly involved in R&D activity. However, this is not the only explanation. The relatively low interest in the R&D-track on the part of the main contingent of trainees (teaching staff - 70%) is explained not only by the labor input and complexity of R&D projects, but also by the fact that research and development are still not very much popular among faculty in Russian universities.

The majority of trainees (63%), mainly teaching staff, has initially chosen the development of advanced educational technologies as a priority track in order to update courses and other curriculum elements. The attractiveness of the T&L-track is obviously due to the fact that the introduction of new technologies, especially online learning, is caused by the trends of the digital transformations in higher education, and, more recently, by a vital necessity in the face of the forced transition to distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The full training cycle was completed by 289 trainees (46% of those registered for the track), having completed 52 group projects.

The AP-track has been chosen as a priority by 20% of trainees, mainly faculty members. Within the framework of the track, it was required to design (or deeply upgrade) an academic degree program as a whole, not a separate curriculum element. The full training cycle was completed by 48 trainees (24% of those registered for the track), having completed 11 group projects. According to the trainees, the AP-track was the most difficult and time consuming, as it involved the design of the program taking into consideration all stages of its life cycle.

For those who moved along the AP-track program, the course "Key faculty competencies in the context of the academic program life cycle: Foresight-Forecast-Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate" was offered. The idea of the course was to systematically outline all stages of the life cycle of a degree program as the main product of a university and to focus on those competencies needed for academic staff at each stage of creating and delivering programs.

The idea of the course is borrowed from the evolution of well-known CDIO approach to engineering education [1]. The CDIO approach was initially developed for basic engineering education focused on Bachelor's training to complex activity at Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate stages of the engineering products life cycle [2]. As a result of evolution, the approach has been adapted to Master programs focused on graduate's training to innovative engineering activities at the stages of Forecast-Conceive-Design-Implement (FCDI) and to PhD programs oriented to postgraduate's training to engineering research at the stages of Foresight-Forecast-Conceive-Design (FFCD). The extensions of FCDI and FFCD of the CDIO structure are due to the need to take into account the system of division of labor in the engineering profession when developing competencies of Bachelors, Masters and PhD-holders in the three-cycle system of engineering education and training to complex, innovative and research activities, respectively. The absence of "Operate" in FCDI structure indicates that this kind of engineering activity (operation and maintenance of products, processes, systems, and services) is not a priority for Masters. The presence of "Forecast" emphasizes the importance for them of predicting potential needs of society in new products, processes, systems, and services. The absence of "Implement" in the FFCD structure indicates that participation in manufacturing is not a priority for PhD-holders. The presence of "Foresight" underlines the importance for research activity of a long-term vision of the society's needs and technological foresight to create a scientific basis for conceiving and designing new products, processes, systems, and services.

By analogy with engineering activities, in scientific and educational activities, there is a system of division of labor between academic staff of divers position in HEI, corresponding to various stages of the life cycle of educational products. Research activities on the creation of scientific basis of educational products and related FFCD stages are a priority for full professors. Methodological activities for the design and development of educational products and related FCDI stages are a priority for associate professors. Teaching activities for the implementation of educational products and related CDIO stages are a priority for assistant professors. For sure, there is no strict division of responsibility and authority between the academic staff of divers positions at the university. However, the priorities do exist and they are known.

The objective of the course "Key faculty competencies in the context of the academic program life cycle: Foresight-Forecast-Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate" was developing competencies of academic staff of divers ranks and positions (assistant,

associate and full professor) for productive and high-quality research and teaching in university system of division of labor.

The course has been offered to trainees by 6 specific modules. The “Foresight” module is devoted to the analysis of promising research & development trends in the subject area; methods of integration of research, innovation and education (knowledge triangle); global trends in STEM higher education. The “Forecast” module is dedicated to forecasting the most demanded educational products based on the analysis of the higher education market, the needs of employers, and the interests of other stakeholders. The “Conceive” module is focused on planning the most competitive academic programs; assessing their feasibility and life-cycle; realizing up-to-date strategies for STEM:IT higher education. The “Design” module is devoted to the design of three-cycle STEM:IT academic programs based on the CDIO-FCDI-FFCD triad [3]. The “Implement” module is dedicated to the creation of teaching & learning materials for rational combination of on-campus and online education and training. The “Operate” module is focused on the delivery of academic programs with the optimal use of PBL, Case Study, and other active learning methods. The results of the course implementation in terms of the demand for modules showed the priority of FFCD modules for full professors, FCDI modules for associate professors and CDIO modules for assistant professors and instructors.

New knowledge and skills acquired by the trainees as the course outcomes allowed them to have designed (or updated) academic programs in IT based on up-to-date STEM:IT strategies and international standards of engineering education adapted to STEM:IT including the latest version of CDIO Standards [4]. After completing the teamwork on the group projects, the trainees were asked to give a self-assessment of the compliance of the newly developed IT programs with the CDIO Standards (Fig. 3) and the ABET accreditation criteria (Fig. 4). The diagrams in the figures are built on the basis of averaged data of self-assessment of developed academic degree programs by the trainees who participated in the development.

To assess the compliance of the developed Bachelor programs with the CDIO Standards, the trainees were recommended to use the 6-level scale Rubrics [5]. From the diagram in Fig. 3 it follows that the trainees managed to get closer to the recommendations of the Core CDIO Standards 3.0 in terms of context for IT higher education (Standard 1), intended learning outcomes (Standard 2), integrated curriculum (Standard 3), design-implement experiences (Standard 5), integrated learning experiences (Standard 7) and enhancement of faculty teaching competence (Standard 10). Less success achieved in terms of introduction to IT higher education (Standard 4), learning workspaces (Standard 6), active learning (Standard 8), enhancement of faculty IT-competence (Standard 9), learning assessment (Standard 11) and program evaluation (Standard 12). Based on the self-assessment results, trainees identified areas for further development and improvement of the IT programs to better comply with CDIO Standards.

To assess the compliance of the developed IT programs with the ABET Criteria, the trainees were recommended to use 2020-2021 Criteria for Accrediting Computing

Programs (<https://www.abet.org/accreditation/accreditation-criteria/>). The programs were assessed on a 3-level scale: 0 - the criterion is not met, 1 - the criterion is partially met, 2 - the criterion is fully met. When self-assessing the developed IT programs, the trainees applied General Criteria for Computing Programs and Program Criteria for various specializations (Computer Science, Cybersecurity, Information Systems, Information Technology).

From the diagram in Fig. 4 it follows that the newly developed IT programs only partially met the ABET accreditation criteria. At the same time, the trainees managed to approach the requirements of the criteria in terms of planning student outcomes (Criterion 3), designing curricula (Criterion 5), developing of faculty qualification (Criterion 6) and providing classrooms, offices, laboratories, and associated equipment (Criterion 7). Unfortunately, the trainees achieved less success in defining the objectives of IT programs (Criterion 2), planning their continuous improvement (Criterion 4) and providing institutional support (Criterion 8). Anyway, as a result of the self-assessment, trainees identified areas for further improvement of the IT programs to better comply with ABET accreditation criteria.

3.1 Figures

Fig. 1. The location of the universities participated in the project

Fig. 2. The complete cycle of faculty training

Fig. 3. Compliance of the developed IT programs with the CDIO Standards

Fig. 4. Compliance of the developed IT programs with the ABET Criteria

4 SUMMARY

In conclusion, it should be stated that despite the unfavorable conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, the pilot project on online training of a large number of academic staff at the International Computer Science CPD Center of Tomsk State University on a wide range of key issues of IT higher education improvement was successful. The project can be considered as one of the best practices for mass advanced online training of academic staff of Russian universities working in IT sector of higher education. The results of the pilot project will be further studied with the aim of further development and improvement of online teaching & learning materials, as well as technologies for the implementation of training programs. However, after the restrictions associated with the COVID-19 pandemic are lifted, it is planned to run faculty training with the use of blended learning. This mode will improve the quality of the trainees teamwork on R&D and educational projects, and overall results of the faculty training.

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